

STRENGTHENING CLINICAL TRIAL REGULATORY AND ETHICAL REVIEW OVERSIGHT IN EAST AFRICA.

D1.5 Exploitation and Dissemination Plan

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ABSTRACT:	This report presents the initial version of the Exploitation and Dissemination Plan for the ACCESSAFRICA 2 project. It summarizes the various strategies to be used to disseminate the project results and other project outcomes.
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Summary

The present Exploitation and Dissemination Plan – prepared within the Coordination and Management Work Package (WP1) – will ensure the communication and dissemination of project results from various WPs.

The document includes all the information needed to facilitate results exploitation of the ACCESSAFRICA 2 project partners.

Despite being a deliverable intended for submission to the European Commission by December 31st within the ACCESSAFRICA 2 project, the Exploitation and Dissemination Plan will undergo regular review and updates to ensure the fulfillment of its objectives, with amendments made if necessary.

1 Introduction to the ACCESSAFRICA 2 Project

ACCESSAFRICA 2 initiative is to Strengthen Clinical Trial Regulatory and Ethical Review oversight in East Africa. Funded under European Union's Horizon 2020 programme for three years (2023-2026). This project is supported by the Global Health EDCPT3 Joint Undertaking and its members. ACCESS AFRICA 2 will have the options to assess, train, review, inspect, and develop guidelines to improve regulatory processes for clinical trials in East Africa.

With the increased number of drug development clinical trials and vaccine development studies for poverty related diseases conducted in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), these increases have not been matched with increase in regulatory support and ethical review in SSA. Specific gaps exist in skills and knowledge in providing adequate regulatory oversight and ethical review and pharmacovigilance.

ACCESSAFRICA 2 recognizes that improved regulatory and ethic review processes for clinical trials will result to strong regulatory and research ethics review environment, and again will increase the ethics and regulatory exposure to research projects.

With increased clinical trials in East Africa, ACCESSAFRICA 2 will contribute to the attainment of the sustainable development goal 3 through supporting innovative research to find solutions to the poverty related diseases in the region.

ACCESSAFRICA 2 builds on an existing consortium AccessAfrica, which is an EDCTP-funded project to improve regulation and ethical review for post-trial access of investigative medicinal products clinical trials in Africa.

ACCESSAFRICA 2 aim is to improve ethical review and regulatory capacity for clinical trials in two Sub-Saharan Africa countries, with specific focus on the review and oversight of reported adverse events during clinical trials, improve efficiencies of the NECs and NRAs, and equip them with skills and knowledge for improved operations during outbreaks and epidemics.

ACCESSAFRICA 2 primary objectives are to

- Increase the regulatory and ethics capacity of NRAs, NECs, and IRBs for review, approval, and oversight of clinical trials in Ethiopia and Uganda.
- Strengthening links between ethics and regulatory functions by establishing collaborative relationships between National Ethics Committee (NEC), National Regulatory Agencies (NRA) and local IRB, and communication among the related actors.
- Build capacity for increased research leadership through collaboration with the Eastern Africa Consortium for Clinical Research (EACCR).

The overall work plan consists of the following four work packages:

WP1 Coordination and management

WP2 Improving regulatory and ethical review and oversight of clinical trials.

WP3 Strengthening linkages between regulatory authorities and ethics review committees.

WP4 Increasing capacity for research leadership in sub-Saharan Africa.

2 General Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication strategy

The rights for disseminating and exploiting intellectual property and know-how will be addressed through a data-sharing agreement, which all partners of ACCESSAFRICA 2 will sign. The guidelines jointly developed within this project will be made available to enhance research ethics capacity and research leadership across Sub-Saharan Africa

The project strives to ensure that all data is made discoverable for exploitation by key stakeholders following publications from the partners. Appropriate dissemination channels will be used for different types of stakeholders to maximize the impact of the information and results of the project. The range of stakeholders set to benefit from the project outcome includes—

- health care professionals and authorities
- employees of the NRAs and NRECSs
- other ethics committee members
- researchers in the project and beyond
- research institutions
- policy makers
- intervening actors
- educators
- not-for-profit organizations
- the broader scientific community
- private and public sectors
- General public

A central objective of the exploitation and dissemination effort is to maximize opportunities for promoting, communicating, and disseminating research results throughout the entire lifespan of ACCESSAFRICA 2 and beyond. This will guarantee that each partner can promptly contribute to and act upon the findings.

The main objective of the communication activities is to develop and launch an efficient and effective platform for communication of knowledge gained throughout the project to various key stakeholders, at national, regional, and international levels.

2.1 Communication activities in ACCESSAFRICA 2

Communication activities in ACCESSAFRICA 2 pursue three specific objectives, namely to:

1. To develop a plan and strategy for communication with a range of stakeholders
2. To setup and launch the communication platform - Webpage
3. To develop a schedule and structure to ensure communication of project developments, outcomes and knowledge gained with consortium partners.

Efficient dissemination, communication, and exploitation of findings play a pivotal role in ensuring the success of high-impact research, especially when the project involves diverse groups of academic and non-academic partners and audiences. WPI serves as a crosscutting work package designed to coordinate communication activities across all work packages. Its primary objectives are to: 1) cultivate a community around the project involving all pertinent stakeholders to ensure long-term impact and utilization of outcomes, 2) establish a readily recognizable project identity, and 3) raise awareness of ACCESSAFRICA 2 at both national and international levels. Based on experience gained in previous projects and with various stakeholders, WPI will thus use a variety of communication channels and tools to:

- disseminate the results and outcomes of the ACCESSAFRICA 2 project.
- effectively communicate throughout the project to involve and actively engage relevant stakeholders as necessary.
- facilitate the full exploitation of results and outcomes by diverse groups and audiences.

Dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities in ACCESSAFRICA 2 are designed to have the following significant impacts:

- 1) enhanced regulatory capacity to conduct clinical trials in sub-Saharan Africa countries, complementing the work of the African Vaccine Regulatory Forum.
- 2) increased common regulatory mechanisms across sub-Saharan Africa countries, including better alignment with regional standards and overarching continental mechanisms such as the African Medicines Agency
- 3) improved efficiency of the National Regulatory Agencies (NRAs) concerning clinical trials oversight.
- 4) lessons and principles that will help continental or regional Regulatory Agencies in sub-Saharan Africa to better define their function, frameworks and capabilities
- 5) ensure a stronger African ownership and leadership of clinical research in sub-Saharan Africa countries.
- 6) improved a better collaboration between NRAs and national and institutional research ethics committees, research integrity offices, and data access committees.

A comprehensive and multi-layered strategy to efficiently publicize and exploit the findings of ACCESSAFRICA 2 will involve contributions from the entire team throughout the entire lifespan of the project.

2.2 Dissemination and use of results for different target groups

DISSEMINATION AND USE OF RESULTS FOR DIFFERENT TARGET GROUPS					
	key staffs of the project partner institutions	Policy makers at different levels (research institutions, RECs)	Experts, academics, researchers, Organizations	Regulatory authorities	Media
Measures and channels:	Hybrid seminars Face-to-face seminars Shared periodic meetings	Stakeholders' dissemination workshops	Stakeholders' dissemination workshops Academic/expert publications. Academic/expert conference presentations. Publications aimed at expert audience	Staffs training in research designs. Staffs training in pharmacovigilance. Trained in review and oversight of vaccine development. Stakeholders' dissemination workshops	Project events open to the press Media appearances/ interviews Media reports
	<p>For all:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Webpage - in English <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EDCPT newsletter • Project partners' institutional websites Deliverables published on webpage. • Social media: Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn Interactive multi-stakeholder Meetings 				

2.3 Different dissemination channels/platforms

2.3.1 Website

There will be a central general project website in English, with information on the project, project partners, research activities and outcomes. The website of the project will be maintained for at least five years following the end of the project (www.accessafrica.uio.no). Regular updates will be available in English, with reciprocal links to the partners' institutional websites to maximize coverage.

2.3.2 Dissemination of project results to project members.

There will be hybrid seminars (virtual and face-to-face) for staffs of the partners institutions. Such meetings are to present and discuss project results and other relevant outcomes.

2.3.3 Social media (Twitter/Facebook/Linkedin)

The utilization of social media plays a role in establishing and sustaining public engagement with the project. UiO will oversee the management of the English Facebook and LinkedIn accounts for the project, and other partners are encouraged to contribute to the social media content. Additionally, an initiative, led by UiO, will be undertaken to disseminate information about ACCESSAFRICA 2 on other social media platforms, such as Research Gate.

2.3.4 Academic publications and conferences

At the international level ACCESSAFRICA 2 project results will be arranged into key themes, to develop peer-reviewed articles, and reports intended for scientific and non- scientific audiences. ACCESSAFRICA 2 results and other significant outputs will be submitted to varied conferences as abstracts or oral presentations. There will be the possibility of sharing project results in newsletters (e.g., EDCPT newsletter). The ACCESSAFRICA 2 Consortium will focus on participating in high-profile academic conferences and workshops organized by national, European, and international organizations that involve and/or represent clinical trial research communities and regulators.

2.3.5 Dissemination workshops

At the national level, dissemination meetings will be organized for different stakeholders. The project results and other project outcomes will be shared to policy makers, research institutions, and research ethics committees. In addition, results will be shared through national scientific conferences, as the annual research ethics conference.

2.3.6 Other interesting events/activities

Any other noteworthy results or events will be shared with partner institutions and prominently featured on the project website and linked to partners' institution websites.

